

EDUCATION AND CULTURE

THE INFLUENCE OF TRADITIONAL PHILOSOPHY ON DANCE PERFORMANCE: A CROSS-CULTURAL STUDY OF PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS IN CHINESE AND KOREAN DANCERS

La Influencia de la Filosofía Tradicional en el Rendimiento de la Danza: Un Estudio Transcultural de los Mecanismos Psicológicos en Bailarines Chinos y Coreanos

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ABSTRACT

Background: Chinese Wang Yangming's philosophy and Korean Seongxue Theory both emphasize the unity of mind and body, self-cultivation, and harmony between the individual and nature. These philosophical principles may influence dancers' psychological states and performance quality. **Objective:** This study investigates how traditional philosophical cognition affects dance performance through the mediating roles of dance stress, dance engagement, and performance self-efficacy. It also examines potential cultural differences between Chinese and Korean dance students. **Methods:** A total of 450 dance majors (225 from China and 225 from Korea) participated in this study. Data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to test the hypothesized relationships among variables within a cross-cultural context. **Results:** The findings indicate that traditional philosophical cognition positively predicts dance performance by reducing dance stress and enhancing dance engagement. Dance stress has a significant negative effect on performance, while dance engagement and performance self-efficacy serve as mediators linking traditional philosophy to performance outcomes. Significant cultural differences were observed in the psychological pathways between the two groups. **Conclusions:** This study provides empirical evidence for integrating traditional philosophical concepts into dance education. The results highlight the importance of addressing stress management and fostering motivation to improve performance and support culturally adaptive training approaches.

KEY WORDS

Dance Psychology, Traditional Philosophy, Dance Stress, Dance Engagement, Performance Self-Efficacy, Cross-Cultural Research.

RESUMEN

Antecedentes: La filosofía de Wang Yangming en China y la teoría Seongxue en Corea enfatizan la unidad de mente y cuerpo, la auto-cultivación y la armonía entre el individuo y la naturaleza. Estos principios filosóficos pueden influir en el estado psicológico de los bailarines y en la calidad de su rendimiento. **Objetivo:** Este estudio analiza cómo la cognición filosófica tradicional afecta el rendimiento de la danza a través de los roles mediadores del estrés en la danza, la implicación en la danza y la autoeficacia. Además, examina las posibles diferencias culturales entre estudiantes de danza de China y Corea. **Métodos:** Participaron un total de 450 estudiantes de danza (225 de China y 225 de Corea). Los datos se analizaron mediante Modelado de Ecuaciones Estructurales (SEM) para probar las relaciones hipotéticas entre las variables en un contexto intercultural. **Resultados:** Los resultados muestran que la cognición filosófica tradicional predice positivamente el rendimiento de la danza al reducir el estrés y aumentar la implicación. El estrés tiene un efecto negativo significativo en el rendimiento, mientras que la implicación y la autoeficacia funcionan como mediadores entre la filosofía tradicional y los resultados de rendimiento. Se observaron diferencias culturales significativas en las vías psicológicas entre los dos grupos. **Conclusiones:** Este estudio ofrece evidencia empírica para integrar conceptos filosóficos tradicionales en la educación en danza. Los resultados destacan la importancia de abordar la gestión del estrés y fomentar la motivación para mejorar el rendimiento y apoyar métodos de formación culturalmente adaptativos.

PALABRAS CLAVE

Psicología de la danza, Filosofía tradicional, Estrés en la danza, Implicación, Autoeficacia, Investigación transcultural.

INTRODUCTION

Research Background

Dance, as a traditional and expressive art form, carries rich cultural connotations and aesthetic values. However, excellent dance performance requires not only solid technical skills but also profound cultural cultivation and psychological qualities (Lan, 2022). Traditional philosophy, as the crystallization of human wisdom, has long influenced artistic creation and appreciation (Halushko & Drannyk, 2023; Keeble, 2005). Nevertheless, systematic investigations of the ways cultural factors influence dance performance through psychological mechanisms remain scarce.

In both China and Korea, Eastern philosophical systems of Wang Yangming's philosophy and Seongxue's Theory highlight principles of 'unity of knowledge and action,' 'self-cultivation,' and 'harmony between heaven and man.' These principles are in consensus with mind-body coordination, profound concentration, and emotional expressions constituting dance art (Chai et al., 2024; Kim, 2022; Luo, 2022). There has been evidence from recent cross-cultural research that philosophical convictions don't only impact artistic production but also form dancers' psychological traits in various cultures (Cordaro et al., 2018). Expanding on these insights and aiming to fill current research gaps, this study examines how Chinese Wang Yangming's philosophy and Korean Seongxue Theory impact dance psychology and performance from a cross-cultural standpoint, establishing a theoretical framework titled 'Traditional Philosophy Cognition—Dance Psychology—Dance Performance'.

Current Research Gaps

There has been growing research into the psychological processes of dance in more recent times, with some addressing the impact of dance stress, dance involvement, and self-efficacy in performing dance on dance performance (Noh, Cho, & Kim, 2009; Walker & Nordin-Bates, 2010). However, these studies have been limited in three important ways (outlined below).

Lack of Systematic Investigation of Traditional Philosophy's Impact on Dance Psychological Mechanisms

Current research primarily focuses on technical training and physiological factors, giving limited attention to cultural psychological factors. For example, while Hanrahan and Vergeer (2001) explored how professional dancers use psychological imagery to enhance performance, they did not examine the role of cultural background in-depth.

Additionally, although Qi (2005) pointed out that modern work habits might harm mental well-being, emphasizing dance's social responsibility in physical and mental health, the study did not empirically analyze how traditional philosophy influences dance psychology.

Limited Cross-Cultural Comparative Research

Existing studies predominantly focus on dancers from single cultural backgrounds and do not systematically compare psychological mechanisms across different cultural contexts. For instance, Hanrahan and Vergeer (2001) primarily investigated Western professional dancers' use of psychological skills without comparing them to dancers from other cultural backgrounds. Meanwhile, in reconsidering Chinese dance anthropology research, Zhao (2020) emphasized the importance of examining dance within specific historical, social, political, religious, and folkloric contexts; nevertheless, concrete cross-cultural comparative studies remain insufficient.

Insufficient Quantitative Model Validation

Although some studies have explored the relationship between philosophy and dance, they have primarily employed qualitative research methods and failed to quantitatively validate their findings using methods such as Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). For example, while Walker and Nordin-Bates (2010) studied professional ballet dancers' experiences of performance anxiety, emphasizing the importance of a sense of control, they did not utilize quantitative methods like SEM. Furthermore, applications of structural equation modeling in cross-cultural psychology research raise validity concerns and other issues that require further investigation (Liu, 1999).

Research Objectives

This study compares the influences of traditional philosophies (Wang Yangming's philosophy and Seongxue Theory) on dance performance from a cross-cultural perspective. Specific objectives include:

1. Examining how traditional philosophical cognition influences dance performance through multiple mediating psychological mechanisms, including dance stress, dance engagement, and performance self-efficacy;
2. Constructing and empirically testing a theoretical model of "Traditional Philosophy—Dance Psychology—Dance Performance" using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM); and
3. Comparing differences between Chinese and Korean dancers in these variable relationships

to enhance understanding of cultural psychological similarities and differences, providing references for cross-cultural dance education practices.

The study collected data from dance majors in Chinese and Korean universities. Research subjects were limited to undergraduate and graduate students majoring in dance-related specialties (such as Chinese Classical Dance, Korean Traditional Dance, Court Dance, etc.). Using convenience sampling, data was collected from 500 target participants, expecting to obtain 450 valid samples after eliminating invalid questionnaires (aiming for equal sample sizes between China and Korea). This method was chosen due to practical constraints in accessing national-level sampling frames and the need to ensure equal representation from both countries. While convenience sampling limits the generalizability of results beyond the surveyed population, it is widely accepted in cross-cultural educational research and allows ecologically valid comparisons within the targeted academic settings.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Traditional Philosophical Cognition and Dance Psychology

Traditional Eastern philosophy, especially Wang Yangming's doctrine in China and Seongxue Theory in Korea, emphasizes key concepts such as the "unity of knowledge and action," "self-cultivation," and "harmony between movement and stillness."

These concepts correspond with the psychological factors of the dance intricacies which include mental-physical synchronization, emotion management, and concentration (Chai et al., 2024; Kim, 2022; Liu, 2024).

Wang's concept regarding the unification of mind and action perceives the understanding and expression of self through movement as one, which is crucial to high level dance performance. Dynamically, self-discipline guided by equilibrium is advocated within Seongxue Theory diagrammatically represented within the Taiji Diagram. Both nurture calmness and coherence while simultaneously fostering stress reduction increasing engagement and performance self-efficacy (Lee, 2022; Moon, 2011; Oh 2015).

Psychological research has recently corroborated these claims. The fusion of dance training with traditional values helps to bolster emotional resilience as well as improve the overall quality of performance (Fauz, Divarathna, & Rajapakse, 2022; Lee, 2024). Furthermore, traditional philosophical

techniques such as mindfulness and meditative concentration relieve an overload of thoughts and allow for the experience of flow with the activity (Fredrickson, 2001; Shusterman, 2008).

Existing literature has studied some aspects of these interrelationships, but most of them are qualitative in nature, lacking empirical corroboration. There continues to be a scarcity of quantitative research exploring the intersection of philosophy, psychology, and dance, especially from a cross-cultural perspective. This research seeks to fill this void by employing Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to analyze how traditional philosophical reasoning impacts performance via dance-related stress, engagement, and self-efficacy.

Dance Psychological Variables Dance Stress

Dance stress has emerged as a psychological factor that has a critical effect on performance outcomes. Unlike general performance anxiety, dance stress specifically relates to the unique pressures of artistic performance, including technical precision, aesthetic expression, and audience engagement (Hanrahan & Vergeer, 2001; Walker & Nordin-Bates, 2010). Research has indicated that dance stress manifests through multiple aspects of dance training and performance. In addition to the intense physical and technical demands of their craft, dancers often experience stress from high performance expectations and perfectionist tendencies (Hong, 2018; Kim, 1997; Noh, 2010). This is further complicated by pressures from social evaluation and competition within the dance environment, as well as challenges in managing rigorous training schedules and time commitments (Hwang, 2011; Lee, 2020).

Professional dance training environments also come with unique stress management-related challenges. Studies have shown that students in professional preparatory or vocational dance training programs bear heavy training loads, which typically increase during rehearsal and performance seasons (Grove, Main, & Sharp, 2013). Beyond physical demands, dance students face multiple psychosocial pressures related to interpersonal relationships, academic requirements, environmental factors, and competition in dance training environments (Blevins et al., 2020b). The management of these various stress factors is crucial for both performance quality and physical well-being.

Dance Engagement

Dance Engagement is relatively intertwined with the Psychological state of dance engagement

or immersion (Ghani & Deshpande, 1994). In that dance, there exists a heightened state of internal focus, automotomic sequences that are seamlessly controlled by the analyzing center. The term engagement, particularly in the context of dance, has transformed and matured with the advancement of research documentation. Current documents focusing on this particular area of focus highlight its importance in optimal performance, peak experience of happiness, and its associated concern in the performance of art (Kim, 2012; Kwon, 2007).

As with artistry does meaning alongside intensive dance, one can easily define the engagement of an individual to do both to achieve defined goals which results in absolute mental concentration and physical pushing of the body as seen in the work of a dancer. Besides, happen, such a sense of engagement attention is required in correct coordination of individual body parts which goes beyond mere use of muscle action as needed. This engagement guarantees the performer, including dancers, a total freedom of feeling of satisfaction along with the ability, control which goes beyond setting limits on expression, guides of controlled mediated level and artistic expression, self-imposed rules acceptance. The state aid not only enhances the artistry but the feeling of psychol. satisfaction strengthens imitation in dance and development artistically.

Performance Self–Efficacy

Performance self-efficacy in dance is a higher-order psychological construct that goes beyond general self-evaluations of confidence, reflecting dancers' particular beliefs about their capacity to execute tasks skillfully. It is particularly useful in the context of dance due to the combined complexities of physical technique, artistry, and emotional readiness that go into performing (Hae-Won & Young-Mee, 2016; Lee 2003). Research has shown performance self-efficacy development to be highly related to dance experience and active participation, and performance frequency and intensity of training have been found to be contributing factors (Lee 2003).

Studies have confirmed that the most successful dancers, who reach the ultimate level of mind-body harmony in performance, receive deep increments of self-efficacy, which manifests as complete immersion in movement and movement performance without the necessity of conscious control (Lee, Kim, & Kim, 2012). This heightened level of performance self-efficacy not only contributes to individual creative performance but also serves a fundamental function in the overall development of dance art. The relationship between self-efficacy and achievement

in performance exhibits impressive consistency across dance and performance sports disciplines, a finding that indicates its inherent contribution in achievement settings (Hwang 2011). Moreover, empirical evidence suggests that performance self-efficacy functions as a pivotal mediator linking dancers' enthusiasm and engagement to both their artistic accomplishment and the overall quality of their performances.

METHODOLOGY

Theoretical Foundation

Integrating theoretical perspectives from cultural psychology, sports psychology, and dance psychology, this study investigates the underlying mechanisms by which traditional philosophical cognition shapes psychological variables in dance and ultimately influences performance outcomes.

Traditional Philosophical Cognition and Cultural Psychology

Cultural psychology has proven that cultural values indeed organize individuals' cognitive style, emotional control, and behavioral tendencies (Markus & Kitayama, 1991). Eastern philosophical systems of internal cultivation, emotion control, and mind-body integration offer distinctive frameworks for describing psychological states for performance contexts. Wang Yangming's theory of the "unity of knowledge and action" stresses the alignment of cognition and behavior, which can minimize cognitive load and stress in dance performance. Seongxue Theory's focus on "self-cultivation" also implies possible avenues for obtaining psychological resilience through rigorous practice and meticulous attentiveness.

Sports Psychology and Dance Psychological Variables

Sport psychology research has firmly established the central position of psychological processes in the mastery of performance (Deci & Ryan, 2000). As an art sport, dance has much in common with competitive sport, especially in stress management, attention control, and confidence building. Research has shown that excessive dance stress can impair both engagement and performance quality (Blevins et al., 2020a; Wilson & Sun, 2021). Studies have also consistently found that highly engaged dancers demonstrate more stable technical execution and stronger stage presence (Critien & Ollis, 2006; Lobo et al., 2022). Moreover, performance confidence has been shown to directly influence movement fluidity and performance stability (Evans, 2013; Kim, Im, & Lee, 2015).

Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses

Based on the above literature review, this study constructs the following theoretical model of Traditional Philosophy Cognition-Dance Psychology-Dance Performance. It tests the following hypotheses:

H1: Traditional philosophical cognition (unity of mind and principle, unity of knowledge and action, yin-yang complementarity, movement-stillness integration) significantly influences dancers' dance stress.

H2: Traditional philosophical cognition significantly influences dancers' dance engagement.

H3: Traditional philosophical cognition significantly influences dancers' performance self-efficacy.

H4: Dance stress has a significant negative impact

on dance engagement.

H5: Dance stress has a significant negative impact on performance self-efficacy.

H6: Dance engagement has a significant positive impact on dance performance.

H7: Performance self-efficacy has a significant positive impact on dance performance.

H8: Dance stress mediates the relationship between traditional philosophical cognition and dance engagement.

H9: Dance engagement mediates the relationship between traditional philosophical cognition and dance performance.

H10: Performance self-efficacy mediates the relationship between traditional philosophical cognition and dance performance.

RESULTS

Sample Characteristics

Table 1: Demographic Variable Frequency Analysis (N=450).

Item	Option	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	76	16.9
	Female	374	83.1
Age	18-20 years	198	44.0
	21-23 years	142	31.6
	24 years and above	110	24.4
Country	China	225	50.0
	Korea	225	50.0
Current Education Level	Undergraduate	291	64.7
	Graduate	159	35.3

Table 2: Sample Dance Characteristics Frequency Analysis (N=450).

Item	Option	Frequency	Percentage
Dance Major	Chinese Classical Dance	139	30.9
	Korean Traditional Dance	163	36.2
	Court Dance	113	25.1
	Others	35	7.8
Years of Dance Study	Less than 1 year	82	18.2
	1-3 years	128	28.4
	4-6 years	164	36.4
	7 years and above	76	16.9
Traditional Philosophy Course Experience	Yes	169	37.6
	No	281	62.4
Extra-curricular Dance Practice Hours	Less than 5 hours	101	22.4
	5-10 hours	121	26.9
	11-15 hours	156	34.7
	Over 15 hours	72	16.0

The sample comprised 450 dance majors, with equal representation from China and Korea (225 each). Female participants (83.1%) significantly outnumbered male participants (16.9%). The majority of participants were aged 18–20 years (44.0%), with Korean Traditional Dance (36.2%) and Chinese Classical Dance (30.9%) as the predominant specializations. Most participants had 4–6 years of dance experience (36.4%) and spent 11–15 hours weekly on extra-curricular dance practice (34.7%). Approximately one-third

(37.6%) of participants had taken traditional philosophy courses.

Measurement Tool Analysis Exploratory Factor Analysis

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test.

KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy	0.941
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity Approx. Chi-Square	6326.904
df	300
Sig.	0.000

Principal component analysis with varimax rotation was conducted to examine the construct validity of the measurement tools. The KMO value of 0.941 and significant Bartlett's test ($\chi^2 = 6326.904$, $p < .001$) verified the data's suitability for factor

analysis. Five factors were extracted, explaining 68.170% of the total variance, with the largest variance explained being 38.875%, revealing no significant common method bias.

Table 4: Rotated Component Matrix.

Items	Components				
	1	2	3	4	5
Traditional Philosophy Cognition 1	0.801				
Traditional Philosophy Cognition 2	0.803				
Traditional Philosophy Cognition 3	0.778				
Traditional Philosophy Cognition 4	0.777				
Traditional Philosophy Cognition 5	0.790				
Dance Stress 1		0.786			
Dance Stress 2		0.749			
Dance Stress 3		0.796			
Dance Stress 4		0.786			
Dance Stress 5		0.776			
Dance Engagement 1			0.766		
Dance Engagement 2			0.743		
Dance Engagement 3			0.749		
Dance Engagement 4			0.728		
Dance Engagement 5			0.760		
Performance Self-Efficacy 1				0.724	
Performance Self-Efficacy 2				0.761	
Performance Self-Efficacy 3				0.751	
Performance Self-Efficacy 4				0.733	
Performance Self-Efficacy 5				0.766	
Dance Performance 1					0.693
Dance Performance 2					0.742
Dance Performance 3					0.739
Dance Performance 4					0.698
Dance Performance 5					0.717

The rotated factor matrix (Table 4) revealed that all items have close relationships with their respective dimensions, and the factor loadings of all items on their respective variables were greater than 0.5,

with no cross-loading issues. This indicates that the factor loading distribution of the rotated component matrix was consistent with the questionnaire design.

Reliability and Validity Analysis

Table 5: Scale Reliability and Validity Results.

Dimension	Items	Cronbach's α	CR	AVE
Traditional Philosophy Cognition	5	0.885	0.885	0.607
Dance Stress	5	0.883	0.884	0.603
Dance Engagement	5	0.886	0.886	0.608
Performance Self-Efficacy	5	0.880	0.880	0.595
Dance Performance	5	0.873	0.873	0.578

All dimensions in the reliability and validity tests showed good internal consistency with Cronbach's α coefficients ranging from 0.873 to 0.886. Composite reliability (CR) values exceeded 0.87, and average variance extracted (AVE) values were all above 0.57, indicating good convergent validity. The square roots of AVE values were greater than the inter-construct correlations, confirming discriminant validity.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

The CFA results confirmed the five-factor structure

of the measurement model. Figure 1 shows the CFA model with standardized factor loadings. For Traditional Philosophy Cognition, the loadings ranged from 0.759 to 0.797; for Dance Stress, from 0.752 to 0.818; for Dance Engagement, from 0.759 to 0.815; for Performance Self-Efficacy, from 0.751 to 0.793; and for Dance Performance, from 0.738 to 0.771. All factor loadings were significant ($p < .001$). The correlations between constructs ranged from -0.33 to 0.67, with Dance Stress showing the expected negative correlations with the other constructs.

Figure 1: Confirmatory Factor Analysis Model with Standardized Factor Loadings.

Table 6: Model Fit Indices.

Fit Index	CMIN/DF	RMSEA	GFI	NFI	CFI	IFI	TLI
Standard Value	<3	<0.08	>0.9	>0.9	>0.9	>0.9	>0.9
Model Value	1.117	0.016	0.951	0.954	0.995	0.995	0.994

The model demonstrated an excellent fit with the data, as shown in Table 6. The CMIN/DF value of 1.117 was well below the recommended threshold of 3, and the RMSEA value of 0.016 indicated an

excellent fit. All other fit indices (GFI, NFI, CFI, IFI, and TLI) exceeded 0.95, providing strong support for the construct validity of the measurement tools.

Statistical Analysis Results Descriptive Analysis

Table 7: Variable Descriptive Analysis.

Variable	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Traditional Philosophy Cognition	1	5	3.198	1.094	-0.447	-1.108
Dance Stress	1	5	2.741	1.064	0.566	-0.922
Dance Engagement	1	5	3.291	1.079	-0.638	-0.809
Performance Self-Efficacy	1	5	3.319	1.059	-0.610	-0.806
Dance Performance	1	5	3.324	1.056	-0.600	-0.824

All variables were measured on a five-point scale. The means ranged from 2.741 to 3.324, signaling moderate levels across variables. The absolute

values of skewness and kurtosis were all less than 2, indicating the data fit a normal distribution.

Correlation Analysis

Table 8: Correlation Analysis.

	Traditional Philosophy Cognition	Dance Stress	Dance Engagement	Performance Self-Efficacy	Dance Performance
Traditional Philosophy Cognition	1				
Dance Stress	-.295**	1			
Dance Engagement	.396**	-.449**	1		
Performance Self-Efficacy	.412**	-.450**	.542**	1	
Dance Performance	.453**	-.484**	.587**	.559**	1

Note: **p<0.01.

The correlation analysis revealed significant relationships between all variables ($p<0.01$).

Traditional Philosophy Cognition showed a negative correlation with Dance Stress ($r=-.295$)

and positive correlations with Dance Engagement ($r=.396$), Performance Self-Efficacy ($r=.412$), and

Dance Performance ($r=.453$), supporting the hypothesized relationships.

Structural Equation Modeling Analysis

Figure 2: Structural Equation Model.

Table 9: Model Fit Test.

Fit Index	CMIN/DF	RMSEA	GFI	NFI	CFI	IFI	TLI
Standard Value	<3 or 5	<0.08 or 0.1	>0.9	>0.9	>0.9	>0.9	>0.9
Model Actual Value	1.171	0.019	0.948	0.952	0.993	0.993	0.992

The model demonstrated excellent fits with all indices, meeting or exceeding standard requirements. The CMIN/DF value of 1.171 and

RMSEA value of 0.019 indicated excellent model fit, while all other fit indices (GFI, NFI, CFI, IFI, and TLI) exceeded 0.95.

Table 10: SEM Path Coefficient Table.

Impact Path	Standardized Path Coefficient	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Traditional Philosophy Cognition → Dance Stress	-0.339	-0.287	0.046	-6.261	***
Traditional Philosophy Cognition → Dance Engagement	0.305	0.282	0.047	5.95	***
Dance Stress → Dance Engagement	-0.415	-0.451	0.059	-7.666	***
Dance Stress → Performance Self-Efficacy	-0.241	-0.275	0.061	-4.536	***
Dance Engagement → Performance Self-Efficacy	0.398	0.417	0.062	6.771	***
Traditional Philosophy Cognition → Performance Self-Efficacy	0.208	0.201	0.048	4.183	***
Traditional Philosophy Cognition → Dance Performance	0.196	0.179	0.044	4.053	***
Dance Engagement → Dance Performance	0.398	0.395	0.059	6.722	***
Performance Self-Efficacy → Dance Performance	0.308	0.292	0.055	5.295	***

Note: *** $p < 0.001$.

All path coefficients were significant ($p < 0.001$). Traditional Philosophy Cognition negatively affected

Dance Stress ($\beta = -0.339$) and positively affected Dance Engagement ($\beta = 0.305$) and Performance

Self-Efficacy ($\beta=0.208$). Meanwhile, Dance Stress negatively influenced both Dance Engagement ($\beta=-0.415$) and Performance Self-Efficacy ($\beta=-$

0.241). Finally, both Dance Engagement ($\beta=0.398$) and Performance Self-Efficacy ($\beta=0.308$) positively influenced Dance Performance.

Mediation Effect Analysis

Table 11: Summary of Direct and Indirect Effects.

Effect Type	Path	Effect Value	SE	95% CI
Single Mediation Effects				
Total Effect	Traditional Philosophy → Dance Performance	0.437	0.052	[0.335, 0.536]
Direct Effect	Traditional Philosophy → Dance Stress → Performance	0.196	0.044	[0.094, 0.282]
	Traditional Philosophy → Dance Engagement → Performance	0.074	0.022	[0.038, 0.122]
	Traditional Philosophy → Dance Engagement → Performance	0.102	0.026	[0.058, 0.158]
	Traditional Philosophy → Self-Efficacy → Performance	0.065	0.020	[0.031, 0.108]

Table 12: Chain Mediation Effects.

Chain Path	Effect Value	SE	95% CI
Traditional Philosophy → Dance Stress → Engagement → Performance	0.040	0.011	[0.022, 0.063]
Traditional Philosophy → Stress → Self-Efficacy → Performance	0.035	0.009	[0.019, 0.056]
Traditional Philosophy → Engagement → Self-Efficacy → Performance	0.049	0.012	[0.030, 0.074]

The mediation analysis revealed significant indirect effects along multiple pathways. The total indirect effect accounted for 55.1% of the total effect (0.241/0.437). Single mediation effects through Dance Stress ($\beta=0.074$), Dance Engagement ($\beta=0.102$), and Performance Self-Efficacy

($\beta=0.065$) were all significant. Furthermore, chain mediation effects through combinations of mediators were also significant, with the strongest chain effect observed through the Dance Engagement → Self-Efficacy pathway ($\beta=0.049$).

Multi-group Analysis

Table 17: Multi-group Analysis.

Impact Path	Korea	P	China	P
	Standardized Path Coefficient		Standardized Path Coefficient	
Traditional Philosophy Cognition → Dance Stress	-0.257	***	-0.434	***
Traditional Philosophy Cognition → Dance Engagement	0.385	***	0.192	0.009
Dance Stress → Dance Engagement	-0.349	***	-0.513	***
Dance Stress → Performance Self-Efficacy	-0.170	0.010	-0.368	***
Dance Engagement → Performance Self-Efficacy	0.500	***	0.268	0.002
Traditional Philosophy Cognition → Performance Self-Efficacy	0.214	0.002	0.164	0.023
Traditional Philosophy Cognition → Dance Performance	0.150	0.025	0.242	***
Dance Engagement → Dance Performance	0.394	***	0.401	***
Performance Self-Efficacy → Dance Performance	0.343	***	0.277	***

Note: * $p<0.05$, ** $p<0.01$, *** $p<0.001$.

The multi-group analysis revealed significant differences between Korean and Chinese dancers along several key pathways. For Chinese dancers, traditional philosophical cognition reduced dance stress ($\beta=-0.434$, $p<0.001$) and influenced dance performance ($\beta=0.242$, $p<0.001$) to greater extents than for Korean dancers. Meanwhile, for Korean dancers, traditional philosophical cognition enhanced dance engagement ($\beta=0.385$, $p<0.001$) and the relationship between dance engagement and performance self-efficacy ($\beta=0.500$, $p<0.001$) more substantially than for Chinese dancers.

Finally, notable cultural differences were also observed in stress management; for Chinese

dancers, dance stress had stronger negative effects on both dance engagement ($\beta=-0.513$, $p<0.001$) and performance self-efficacy ($\beta=-0.368$, $p<0.001$) than for Korean dancers. These findings highlight distinct cultural patterns in the impacts of traditional philosophical cognition on dance psychological variables and performance outcomes.

DISCUSSION

Utilizing theoretical frameworks from cultural psychology, sports psychology, and dance psychology, this study explores how traditional philosophical cognition (Chinese Wang Yangming's philosophy and Korean Seongxue Theory)

influences dance performance through dance psychological variables (dance stress, dance engagement, performance self-efficacy). This section provides an in-depth explanation of the study's academic contributions and cross-cultural findings, discusses the theoretical and practical implications of its results, and outlines its limitations as well as potential directions for future research.

Hypothesis Testing Results Analysis

The influence mechanism of traditional philosophy, as an important form of cultural cognition, on dance performance is complex. After reviewing existing research, the following hypotheses were developed, tested, and verified.

Traditional Philosophical Cognition Has Significant Effects on Dance Psychological Variables

Traditional philosophical cognition significantly reduces dance stress (H1 supported), indicating that philosophical training may help dancers better manage psychological stress and maintain emotional stability. Traditional philosophical cognition significantly increases dance engagement (H2 supported), suggesting that philosophical training may enhance dancers' concentration and persistence in dance. Finally, traditional philosophical cognition significantly strengthens performance self-efficacy (H3 supported), showing that philosophical training may help dancers build confidence and improve stage presence.

Mechanisms of Dance Psychological Variables' Impact on Dance Performance

Dance stress significantly reduces dance engagement (H4 supported), aligning with the "stress-performance inverted U-shaped curve" theory in sports psychology and suggesting that while moderate stress helps improve performance, excessive stress weakens concentration (Blevins et al., 2020b). Dance stress significantly reduces performance self-efficacy (H5 supported), indicating that higher stress leads to lower psychological stability and movement fluidity in dancers' stage performance (Silva Constantino, Prado, & Lofrano-Prado, 2011). Dance engagement significantly enhances dance performance (H6 supported), supporting Flow Theory and indicating that high engagement can improve movement fluidity and stage presence (Gonzalez-Sanchez et al., 2019). Performance self-efficacy significantly enhances dance performance (H7 supported), suggesting that dancers with higher confidence levels can better control the stage and deliver higher quality performances (Evans, 2013; Xie &

Yoon, 2024).

Traditional Philosophical Cognition Indirectly Influences Dance Performance Through Mediating Variables

Dance stress mediates the relationship between traditional philosophical cognition and dance engagement (H8 supported), indicating that traditional philosophy can indirectly enhance engagement by reducing stress. Dance engagement mediates the relationship between traditional philosophical cognition and dance performance (H9 supported), suggesting that philosophically cognizant dancers more easily enter flow states and, as a result, enjoy improved performance. Performance self-efficacy mediates the relationship between traditional philosophical cognition and dance performance (H10 supported), indicating that philosophical cognition can indirectly improve performance quality by enhancing confidence.

Cross-Cultural Comparison

This study applied Multi-Group Analysis (MGA) to explore cross-cultural differences. The results revealed distinct mechanisms through which philosophical cognition influences dance psychology in Chinese and Korean dancers. Specifically, the pathway whereby traditional philosophical cognition reduces dance stress more strongly affected Chinese dancers ($\beta = -0.434$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that Wang Yangming's concept of «unity of knowledge and action» might be more effective in helping dancers alleviate stress. This philosophical belief emphasizes consistency between cognition and behavior, making Chinese dancers more inclined to adjust their psychological states through active behavior when facing dance stress, thereby reducing anxiety and stress levels. This phenomenon aligns with the concepts of "self-regulation" and "internal control" in Eastern culture (Markus & Kitayama, 1991), meaning Chinese dancers tend to use philosophical cognition for self-emotional management, actively regulating psychological states during training and performance and thereby reducing the effects of external environmental interference on emotions.

Meanwhile, the pathway whereby traditional philosophical cognition enhances dance engagement more strongly affected Korean dancers ($\beta = 0.385$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that Seongxue Theory's concept of «self-cultivation» might be more effective in promoting dancers' concentration. This concept emphasizes individual discipline and focus, making Korean dancers inclined to view dance more as a cultivation process than merely skill training (Kim, 2022). Moreover, Korean traditional dance (such as court dance) emphasizes meditation and breath

control, which may further enhance dancers' "sense of engagement," promoting high concentration during training. Chinese dancers' dance engagement, however, is more influenced by training methods and personal goal orientation; they tend to motivate themselves through external goal setting (such as competition results, mentor feedback) rather than relying entirely on philosophical cognition's self-disciplinary adjustment.

Overall, while Chinese and Korean dancers share certain psychological mechanisms, the ways philosophical cognition functions differ subtly across cultural backgrounds. This suggests that those applying traditional philosophy in psychological interventions for dancers need to fully consider the influences of cultural background. The integration of more psychological adjustment training based on "unity of knowledge and action" (such as dance meditation and mindfulness training) could help Chinese dancers actively regulate stress at the cognitive level. Meanwhile, applications of the concept of "self-cultivation" (through, for example, establishing dance meditation courses) could help Korean dancers enter deep concentration states during training. To optimize philosophy-based psychological training methods, make them more culturally adaptive, and improve dancers' psychological resilience and artistic expressiveness, future studies should explore the regulatory mechanisms of dance psychological variables in dancers with different cultural backgrounds.

CONCLUSION

This study makes three main theoretical contributions. First, it fills the gap in cross-disciplinary research between traditional philosophy and dance psychology, quantitatively validating the ways in which traditional philosophical cognition influences dance psychological variables and thereby expanding the research perspective of dance psychology. Second, it extends cross-cultural research on dance psychological variables, revealing differences in stress management, confidence building, and concentration enhancement between Chinese and Korean dancers and thereby providing references for future research. Finally, by introducing traditional philosophy as a psychological intervention tool, this study finds that Wang Yangming's philosophy and Seongxue Theory can help dancers optimize their psychological states, making them useful theoretical foundations for future dance psychological training.

From a practical perspective, this study's results have important implications for the optimization of dance education and psychological training systems. Encouraging more psychological adjustment training based on "unity of knowledge and action" (such as

dance meditation and mindfulness training) could help Chinese dancers actively regulate stress at the cognitive level. Meanwhile, the further integration of the concept of "self-cultivation" (for example, establishing dance meditation courses to help dancers enter deep concentration states during training) could substantially benefit Korean dancers. Moreover, to enhance dancers' psychological resilience and artistic expressiveness, practitioners of dance psychological training should actively consider cultural backgrounds and explore more adaptive psychological regulation strategies.

In conclusion, this study empirically validates the mechanism of traditional philosophical cognition in dance psychology and finds differences in philosophical cognition's influence on dance psychological variables across cultural backgrounds, expanding the scope of dance psychology research while providing new insights for dance education and psychological training. To deepen the application of traditional philosophy in dance psychology, develop more culturally adaptive psychological training strategies, and ultimately optimize dancers' mental health and artistic expressiveness, future studies should further explore the influence of philosophical cognition on dance psychological variables for different dance types and cultural backgrounds and from different neuroscientific perspectives.

Significantly, in addition to bridging traditional philosophy with contemporary dance practice, this study provides empirical evidence supporting the value of cultural integration in performing arts education. The findings suggest that incorporating traditional philosophical elements into dance training programs could enhance dancers' technical proficiency and psychological well-being. Furthermore, the cross-cultural comparative approach offers valuable insights for international dance education and cultural exchange programs.

Future research directions could include:

1. Longitudinal studies tracking the long-term effects of philosophical training on dance performance;
2. Investigations of specific traditional philosophy-derived meditation and mindfulness practices and their impacts on dance training;
3. Development of culturally-sensitive psychological intervention programs for dance education;
4. Explorations of the ways different dance genres might benefit from various aspects of traditional philosophical teachings; and
5. Integration of neuroscientific methods to understand the underlying mechanisms of philosophy-based dance training.

These research implications could contribute to the development of more holistic and culturally-informed approaches to dance education and performance training.

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